

Lemma on Combinatorial Geometric Series with Binomial Coefficients

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Abstract: This paper presents lemmas and its corollaries on the combinatorial geometric series and summation of series of binomial coefficients. Also, the coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-12]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-12] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

3. Lemma on Binomial Coefficient

The binomial expansion for binomial coefficients in combinatorial geometric series is used to prove the following lemma.

Lemma 3. 1: $V_{k-1}^{n+1} = V_k^{n+1} - V_k^n$.

Proof. Let us prove this lemma using the binomial expansion for coefficients of combinatorial geometric series.

$$\begin{aligned}
V_k^{n+1} - V_k^n &= \frac{(k+1)(k+2)\cdots(k+n)(k+n+1)}{(n+1)!} - \frac{(k+1)(k+2)\cdots(k+n)}{(n+1)!} \\
&= \frac{(k+1)(k+2)\cdots(k+n)}{n!} \left(\frac{k+n+1}{n+1} - 1 \right) \\
&= \frac{k(k+1)(k+2)\cdots(k+n)}{(n+1)!} = V_{k-1}^{n+1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the lemma is proved.

Lemma 3.2:
$$\sum_{i=1}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i = 2^n - 1$$

Proof. Let us prove this lemma using the summation of series of binomial coefficients and sum of combinatorial geometric series

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=0}^n 2^i &= 2^{n+1} - 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i = 2^n - 1. \\
\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} &= 2^n \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n - 1.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the lemma is proved.

Corollary 3.1:
$$\sum_{i=k}^{n-1} 2^i = 2^n - 2^k.$$

Corollary 3.2:
$$\sum_{i=k+1}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n - \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)\cdots(i+n-i)}{(n-i)!},$$

where
$$\sum_{i=0}^k V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(i+1)(i+2)\cdots(i+n-i)}{(n-i)!}.$$

Corollary 3.3:
$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=k+1}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} - V_k^{n+1}.$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, lemmas and its corollaries were introduced on the combinatorial geometric series and series of binomial coefficients. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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